

MAELSTROM

MArinE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management

D1.1

Set up of project structures

26/01/2021

MAELSTROM

General Information

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Authoring & Approval

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V0.4	25/01/2021	Fantina Madricardo	Tables completed, minor editing and formatting
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Executive Summary

The MAELSTROM project aims to test and evaluate innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in different coastal environments, assessing also their impact on the ecosystems in chosen demo sites and evaluating the economic and societal benefits of the MAELSTROM solutions within local economies. Treatments of the plastic litter for their recovery within a circular economy concept are also foreseen. To achieve some of its pursued objectives, the MAELSTROM project contemplates a series of specific actions to increase social awareness and engage society about the marine litter issue. In this context, engagement of citizens and non-scientific stakeholders will be approached through workshops, stakeholder meetings, capacity building trainings, and a specific app. Citizens will also participate in clean up campaigns. The purpose of the Deliverable D1.1 is to provide detailed information about the project management structures and to define the relevant components of the Project Team to ensure the coordination of the project progress and liaison between the consortium members, associated consortium and Advisory Group members, the EC and third parties.

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1 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex question of the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy. MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with full-fledged circular economy and societal oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) sets out a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort marine litter; (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions providing also a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) enhances social awareness about the marine litter issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

2 MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of:

	National Council Research	CNR	Project Coordinator Fantina MADRICARDO fantina.madricardo@ismar.cnr.it
	Deltares	Deltares	Frans BUSCHMAN Frans.Buschman@deltares.nl
	University of Malta	UOM	Luciano MULE' STAGNO luciano.mule-stagno@um.edu.mt
	The International Sustainable Development Initiatives	ISDI	Manuel SCARPA m.scarpa@isdigroup.com
	Gees Recycling Srl	GEES	Giorgio BETTETO geesretracking@gmail.com
	Venice Lagoon Plastic Free	VLPF	Davide POLETTO d.poletto@plasticfreevenice.org
	CIMA Foundation Research	CIMA	Isabel GOMES isabel.gomes@cimafoundation.org
	TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION	TECNALIA	Damien SALLÉ damien.salle@tecnalia.com
	ALPHA Consult	ALPHA UK	Emiliano SPALTRO es@alphacons.eu
	Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research	CIIMAR	Isabel SOUSA-PINTO ispinto@ciimar.up.pt
	Servizi Tecnici	ST	Nicola FERRARI n.ferrari@stvenezia.com

	The Great Bubble Barrier	TGBB	Philip EHRHORN philip@thegreatbubblebarrier.com
	MAKEEN	MAKEEN	Anders BJORN ABJ@makeenenergy.com
	National Center for Scientific Research	CNRS	Marc GOUTTEFARDE marc.gouttefarde@lirmm.fr

3 Aims of the Deliverable

This document summarises the internal organisation of the MAELSTROM project with the objectives to ensure:

- a. Efficient execution and integration of the project activities
- b. Achievement of project deliverables
- c. Efficient internal communications within the project
- d. Effective dissemination of project activities to the scientific community and general public.

The document is based on information already agreed by partners in the Grant Agreement and in the Consortium Agreement, supplemented by more detailed arrangements made since the start of the project, and includes reference to:

1. Organisational structure and decision-making mechanisms
2. Sharing and distribution of roles/responsibilities
3. Facilitating top-down and bottom-up communication between EU and the partners, ensuring the appropriate information exchange
4. Internal and external coordination procedures
5. Communication management (internal and external)
6. Project Reporting
7. Project meetings
8. Project Support Tools.

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The objective of the document is thus to provide more detail or updated information with respect to the information already available in the Grant Agreement and in the Consortium Agreement, not to duplicate, and certainly not to supersede those documents.

The present document is provided for information only and in no way changes the legal rights and obligations of the partners as described by the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

4 Project documentation

The legal rights and obligations of the MAELSTROM partners are defined in:

The **MAELSTROM Grant Agreement (GA)**, as signed by the Research Executive Agency (REA) and by the coordinator CNR on 18/09/2020, H2020 project reference 101000832, associated with document Ref. Ares(2020)4896415 - 18/09/2020. All other MAELSTROM partners acceded to this GA by subsequently signing the Accession Form A with CNR.

The GA consists of the base contract (signed by REA) and six annexes, of which Annex I, Description Of Action (DOA) describes in detail the work to be performed. The DOA is itself divided into Part A and B. Part A defines all project activities via Work Packages (WP), project deliverables (timing, content, partner responsibilities), milestones (key events), efforts per partner/WP. Part B gives further information on the project organisation including scientific methodology, management structure and procedures, a description of the partners, resources to be committed to the project and expected impacts of the project.

The **MAELSTROM Consortium Agreement (CA)**, version 4 dated 11/11/2020, is signed by all MAELSTROM partners. The MAELSTROM CA, is based upon REGULATION (EU) No 1290/2013 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 11 December 2013, laying down the rules for the participation and dissemination in "Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020)", and the European Commission Multibeneficiary General Model Grant Agreement and its Annexes.

MAELSTROM GA and CA have been distributed to all partners and a copy is maintained by the coordinator on the CNR Repository, as well as on the password-protected MAELSTROM Owncloud shared folder accessible only to project partners.

Other internal project documents (confidential/restricted deliverables, working documents, etc.) and data will be shared via SeedDMS, <https://www.seeddms.org/>, on

open-source document management system that will be installed by the Coordinator.

External project documents (public deliverables, etc.) will be made available to the public via the MAELSTROM web site.

Key documentation from the EU is provided on the EU Participants Portal and includes the AGA-Annotated Model of Grant Agreement, V. 5.2 - 26-06-2019, containing all guidance on the model grant agreement available for readers with any practical questions they may have about particular parts of the GA.

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf

5 Governance structure

The management structure of the Project (see Fig.1) shall comprise the following Consortium Bodies:

Figure 1 – MAELSTROM Management structure

In the following sections the relevant figures in the Project Team will be appointed to ensure the coordination of the project.

5.1 Project Coordinator

The Project Coordinator is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Funding Authority. The Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it, as described in the Grant Agreement and in the Consortium Agreement.

The Project Coordinator (PC), [Fantina Madricardo \(CNR\)](#), is the overall responsible of the project and she is the unique contact for the European Commission. The PC will chair the General Assembly, the Steering Committee (SC), the Implementation Team (ImT) and the External Advisory Board (EAB) and will call for General Assembly, SC, ImT and EAB meetings. The PC will be supported by the Project Management Team (PMT), a dedicated experienced team at CNR and by the Innovation Manager and the Data Manager. A regular assessment process for the proper implementation of the Project will be carried out with the help of the ImT through an intense and continuous communication and information exchange with WP leaders and partners. The successful management of the Project will be achieved also through the implementation of a dedicated open-source Project Management and Team Communication Platform adapted to the Project's requirements.

5.2 General Assembly

The General Assembly is the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium and meets in person at least once a year. Specific and exclusive tasks of the General Assembly are:

- (a) deciding upon major changes in the work, particularly termination, creation, or reallocation of activities;
- (b) deciding any substantial reduction or increase of any Party's Project share;
- (c) deciding of entry of a new entity to the Project and approval of the settlement on the conditions of the accession to the Project, including the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement, of such new entity;
- (d) requesting EC to terminate the participation of a Defaulting Party in accordance with Article 4.2;
- (e) deciding to suspend all or part of the Project or to terminate all or part of the Parties, or to request the EC to terminate the participation of one or more Party/ies;
- (f) proposals to the EC for a change of the Coordinator should be declared as a Defaulting Party;

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- (g) agreeing procedures and policies in accordance with the Commission rules, for knowledge and IPR management.

The General Assembly is composed of one representative of each consortium member (in case two names are indicated the second name indicates the possible substitute) and it is chaired by the MAELSTROM Project Coordinator. In the case of a tie, the Project Coordinator will exercise the decisive vote. It has been ascertained that all General Assembly Members have been empowered to make decisions on behalf of their organisation.

The representative of the General Assembly as indicated by the partners are listed in Table 1.

Table 1- MAELSTROM General Assembly representatives

Partner n°	Partner short name	Partner GA representative
1	CNR	Vanessa Moschino
2	Deltares	Frans Buschman
3	UOM	Marija Demicoli
4	ISDI	Manuel Scarpa
5	GEES	Franco Mioni
6	VLPF	Davide Poletto
7	CIMA	Massimiliano Rosso/Isabel Gomez
8	TECNALIA	Mariola Rodríguez
9	ALPHA UK	Emiliano Spaltro/Elizabeth A. Nerantzis
10	CIIMAR	Isabel Sousa-Pinto
11	ST	Nicola Ferrari
12	TGBB	Francis Zoet
13	MAKEEN	Anders Bjorn
14	CNRS	Marc Gouttefarde

5.3 Project Steering Committee (SC)

The MAELSTROM Project Steering Committee is the consortium's supervisory body for the execution of the Project, which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly. The Committee shall solve conflicts within the Consortium that could not be resolved by the other management bodies or by the MAELSTROM Project Coordinator. It will be responsible for undertaking the strategic planning and direction of the Project, monitoring the Project progress and the revision of its

achievements through the milestones and risk assessment, in accordance with the risk assessment and mitigation plan and its follow-up, the approval of the periodic technical and financial reports, the final report and the Project deliverables before submission to the EC, the approval of networking activities with other related European Projects and initiatives, the approval of the dissemination and communication plan and of the exploitation plan, and the monitoring of their deployment. Therefore, the SC will act as Project Executive Board assuming the executive decisions in relevant management aspects. The SC is composed by one representative of each consortium member (in case two names are indicated for a partner the second name indicates the possible substitute) and chaired by the MAELSTROM Project Coordinator.

The representatives of the SC of each partner are summarized in Table 2

Table 2- MAELSTROM SC representatives

Partner n°	Partner short name	Partner SC representative
1	CNR	Vanessa Moschino
2	Deltares	Frans Buschman
3	UOM	Marija Demicoli
4	ISDI	Manuel Scarpa
5	GEES	Giorgio Betteto
6	VLPF	Davide Poletto
7	CIMA	Massimiliano Rosso/Isabel Gomez
8	TECNALIA	Mariola Rodríguez
9	ALPHA UK	Elizabeth A. Nerantzis
10	CIIMAR	Isabel Sousa-Pinto
11	ST	Nicola Ferrari
12	TGBB	Francis Zoet
13	MAKEEN	Anders Bjorn
14	CNRS	Marc Gouttefarde

5.4 Implementation Team (ImT)

The Implementation Team (ImT), is in charge of the overall supervision of the 3 main pillar activities of MAELSTROM, as follows:

- 1) marine biology,
- 2) Marine Litter (ML) removal technology,

3) circular economy of ML.

Due to the complexity and interdisciplinarity embedded in the Project, the ImT will include representatives of the Consortium (CNR for marine ecosystem monitoring and assessment, TECNALIA and TGBB for ML removal technology, MAKEEN and GEES for green chemistry and circular economy). The ImT responsibilities include:

- (a) the coordination of the various technical activities of the project, ensuring that the technical deliverables are consistent and timely delivered;
- (b) Supporting the technical activity leaders (WP Leaders and Task Leaders) and partners in case of a deadlock situation within their activity.

Specifically, the Consortium has identified the following representatives for the ImT (Table 3).

Table 3- MAELSTROM Project Implementation Team

Pillar	Lead Participant Short Name	Implementation team representatives
Marine Biology	CNR	Vanessa Moschino vanessa.moschino@ismar.cnr.it
Marine litter removal technologies	TECNALIA /TGBB	Damien Sallé damien.salle@tecnalia.com Philip Ehrhorn philip@thegreatbubblebarrier.com
Green chemistry and circular economy	MAKEEN / GEES	Anders BJORN ABJ@makeenenergy.com Giorgio BETTETO geesretracking@gmail.com

5.5 External Advisory Board

An external Advisory Board (EAB) will be appointed in the first month of the Project and will be chaired by the PC. They will provide independent advice and feedback on the application of research to achieve the Project objectives, the integration of interdisciplinary research, communication with all stakeholder groups and the dissemination of research findings and exploitable results. The EAB will be expected to encourage the promotion and wide awareness of the Project amongst their respective communities.

The board will be composed of 3 external senior experts on 3 main pillars:

- 1) marine biology,
- 2) ML removal technology,
- 3) circular economy of ML.

The EAB shall meet once a year in conjunction with major events of the Project, with funding for covering travel and subsistence allocated to the Project Coordinator.

The proposed external senior experts are as follows:

- (a) Prof. Simonetta Frascchetti, professor of Marine Biology, University Federico II of Naples, Italy (marine biology),
- (b) Prof. Frédéric Boyer, Prof. In robotics technology, Laboratoire LS2N Nantes, France (ML removal technology), and
- (c) Dr. Andreja Palatinus, practitioner in circular economy and waste valorisation processes, responsible for the Circular Economy unit at the Chamber of Commerce of Slovenia (circular economy of ML).

The PC will ensure that a non-disclosure agreement is subscribed between all Parties and each EAB member. Its terms shall be not less stringent than those stipulated in this Consortium Agreement, and it shall be concluded no later than 30 calendar days after their nomination, or before any confidential information will be exchanged, whichever date is earlier. The Coordinator shall write the minutes of the EAB meetings and prepare the implementation of the EAB's suggestions. The EAB members shall be allowed to participate in the SC meetings upon invitation but shall not have any voting right.

5.6 Project Management Team (PMT)

The Project management Team (PMT) appointed by CNR will support the PC in the day-to-day activities. The PMT includes a *technical Project manager*, an *administrative/financial manager* and the members of the CNR project office. The PMT will:

- (a) take over all the financial management issues related to the Project activity;
- (b) support and report to the PC for all administrative and quality related issues;
- (c) be responsible for ensuring that the project implements the established quality procedures;
- (d) follow all Project internal administrative activities, in particular related to report preparation.

The PMT reports to the Project Coordinator but closely collaborate with the ImT as needed.

Table 4- MAELSTROM Project Management Team

Name	Role	Contacts
Fantina Madricardo	Project Coordinator	fantina.madricardo@ismar.cnr.it skype: fantinam office phone: +393474983049 mobile: +393474983049
Vanessa Moschino	Coordinator support	vanessa.moschino@ismar.cnr.it
Patricia Sclafani	Scientific Secretary	patricia.sclafani@cnr.it
Emma D'Acunzo	Financial/administrative support	progetti@ismar.cnr.it
Laura Barbieri	Financial/administrative support	progetti@ismar.cnr.it
Loredana Alfaré	Financial/administrative support	progetti@ismar.cnr.it
Elisabetta Borella	Financial/administrative support	progetti@ismar.cnr.it
To be defined	Technical Project Manager	To be defined

5.7 Innovation Manager

The Innovation Manager (IM), [Elizabeth A. Nerantzis \(ALPHA UK\)](#), will have the responsibility of governing the innovation management process that will be implemented by adopting a hybrid research and innovation methodology. She will iteratively consider the evolution of products and market demands, the business strategies of the enterprises present in the consortium, and the results achieved to adjust Project objectives and requirements, specifying the innovations on which MAELSTROM should focus more and identifying exploitation potentials. The IM coordinates the Project activities that will pave the way for innovation and possible market uptake. She is responsible for the innovation management and exploitation plan within the Project and follows up on this plan, coordinating exploitation activities across partners.

5.8 Data Manager

He/she ([still to be appointed by CNR](#)) will coordinate the data management of the Project to assure usability, accountability and quality of the data and valorise it, either by using it for other market applications when possible and relevant or by making the open to the scientific community. He will thus lead the Data

Management Plan and the participation of MAELSTROM in the Open Data Pilot, implementing and overseeing the DMP methodology to assure good data management and valorisation.

5.9 Work Package and Task Leaders

WP and Task Leaders are responsible for the management of their respective activity. Task Leaders are assigned in agreement with the respective Work Package Leader. Task Leaders responsibilities consist of:

- Coordinating the tasks and activities towards the Activity objectives;
- Ensuring a smooth running and co-ordination with other Work Packages and/or Tasks;
- Monitoring of the activity progress with respect to activity goals, milestones, results adequacy.

The structure of the WPs and tasks is summarized in Fig.2.

Figure 2 - MAELSTROM Work Packages and tasks

Table 5- MAELSTROM Work Packages

WP	Work Package Title	Lead Participant Short Name	WP Leader Name
1	Project management and coordination	CNR	Fantina Madricardo fantina.madricardo@ismar.cnr.it
2	ML distribution and ecosystem assessment	CNR	Vanessa Moschino vanessa.moschino@ismar.cnr.it
3	Seabed and lower water column cleaning Technology Cable-based robotic Platform	TECNALIA	Mariola Rodríguez mariola.rodriguez@tecnalia.com
4	Surface/water column cleaning technology	TGBB	Philip Ehrhorn philip@thegreatbubblebarrier.com
5	ML Removal in Selected Demonstration Sites	Deltares	Frans Buschman frans.buschman@deltares.nl
6	Circular economy and sustainability	TECNALIA	Damien Sallé damien.salle@tecnalia.com
7	Coordination and Integration of blue technology for plastic strategy-oriented efforts	CIIMAR	Isabel Sousa-Pinto isabel.sousa.pinto@gmail.com
8	Economic feasibility, social acceptance	ALPHA UK	Elizabeth A. Nerantzis en@alphacons.eu
9	Dissemination, communication, and exploitation of results	CIMA	Isabel Gomes isabel.gomes@cimafoundation.org

6 Conclusion

This document assembles information on project management from the legally-binding documents (Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement) and provides more detail and updates where appropriate.